

METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A NON-NATIVE AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11409848>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-May 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 25-May 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 31-May 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

methodology, Russian language, foreign language, teaching, non-native, word.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the basic concepts of methodology for teachers of Russian as a foreign language, providing methodological assistance in the preparation of educational material in the absence of a language environment and the organization of the educational process at the initial stage.

Introduction. The word "methodology" comes from the Greek "metodos", which means "path". Now this word is used in two meanings.

1. A set of techniques, methods, and forms of work of a teacher in teaching any subject, i.e., the art and skill of a teacher.

2. A science that studies the possibilities and means of achieving the maximum result of the learning process, i.e. the theory of teaching a subject.

In the future, the object of our attention will be methodology as a science, as a theory of teaching Russian to foreign students.

Methodical science was born out of practice in order to comprehend it and highlight positive experiences. The development of science and practice takes place in full cooperation. It is well known that theory is always enriched by practice. But at the same time, practice can be successfully carried out only when it is based on certain knowledge, theoretical prerequisites and patterns.

Methodology is a theoretical and applied science in which the teacher's art, his ability to adapt general methodological recommendations to specific learning conditions will always be of great importance.

In the audience of non-philological students, the Russian language as an academic subject is assimilated not as a system of linguistic phenomena, not for the purpose of describing it, but as a means of communication in written and oral form. Russian language for this category of students, the methodology formulates the task of learning the Russian language in order to participate in language communication, i.e. the task of teaching speech activity in Russian: reading, speaking, listening, writing. This is the academic subject that we should be studying. In methodological science, this approach to learning has been called communicative.

It should be remembered here that even at the end of the XIX century. linguists came to the idea that language and speech are

interrelated, but different concepts. The Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure wrote on this occasion: "Without a doubt, both these subjects are closely related and mutually assume each other: language is necessary for speech to be understandable and produce its effect; speech, in turn, is necessary for language to be established; historically, the fact of speech always precedes language." So, if language is a system of means of communication, then speech is the implementation of this system.

Language teaching as a means of speech communication is the main methodological approach that defines methodological science. At the same time, the methodology deals with clarifying specific goals, defining the content, techniques and methods of teaching, as well as the use of various learning tools.

The initial stage of education, generally recognized by teachers and methodologists, is the most important and difficult period, this period largely determines the further study of a foreign language.

Speaking about the methods of communicating knowledge and instilling skills and abilities to students in relation to the initial stage of learning any foreign language, it is necessary to cite several provisions from the general methodology of teaching foreign languages.

The first, decisive problem of learning is the need to keep the proportions between explanation (comprehension of language material) and practice-training. One understanding is not enough, just as one training is not enough, at the initial stage it is especially important to avoid a gap between knowledge, skills and abilities.

The role of repetition at the initial stage is indisputable, but excessive repetition dulls the attention of students, and creative activity is necessary to mobilize students.

The second problem is the need for the interconnection of oral speech, reading and writing. The new material must first be assimilated orally and be larger in volume than the one that is perceived visually, i.e. read.

At the initial stage, the reading process and especially the writing process of students is still very slow. Oral training serves to overcome this slowness, and for the initial stage, the repeatability factor is very important, because oral training develops hearing, auditory perception and auditory memory. At the initial stage of learning, oral speech is a source for reading, i.e. what is first worked out in oral speech is read.

Reading at the initial stage is useful if the reading material is not difficult. Slow reading of a very difficult text at the initial stage destroys oral speech skills, contributes to the appearance of broken structures (relatively rare constructions for this stage come into conflict with previously learned necessary everyday constructions).

Russian as a foreign language is the most urgent problem in the field of teaching Russian as a foreign language. This is the solution to the issue of providing students with educational material in the Russian language.

Let's take a closer look at the issue of preparing educational material on the Russian language for a non-philological profile. This is a difficult question, since the students in the classroom are mostly non-philologists.

For foreign non-philological students, Russian is not a major subject, it is not an object of specialization, but only a means of acquiring it. It follows that language teaching should introduce them to communication as early as possible, introduce them to the specifics of

spoken language.

After all, in one group you can meet students with different professional orientations: lawyer, economist, physicist, mathematician, philologist, historian and just a lover of Russian culture, literature and language.

We believe that methodological developments of educational materials on the Russian language, first of all, should reflect the communicative orientation of learning. The object of study should be speech activity, the language itself is perceived as the objective basis of speech activity.

Students should acquire the ability to participate in language communication in Russian, especially in the main types of speech activities of language communication, meaning listening, reading, speaking and writing. The objective basis of this communication is the sublanguage of the studied area, represented by a certain topic, certain situations and a certain set of linguistic means.

Teaching Russian as a foreign language began to develop widely in our country only since the late 40s. The first students from different countries began to come to the Soviet Union for education after the end of the Great Patriotic War. Over the years, the number of foreign students in our universities has been increasing.

There was a need to create special departments of the Russian language for foreigners. The first such department was established in 1951 at Lomonosov Moscow State University. The main task of such departments was to teach foreign students practical language skills.

Over the past time, positive experience has already been accumulated in teaching Russian to foreign students. The departments of Russian as a foreign language not only at Moscow State University, but also at other major universities in our country, played a major role in the accumulation and understanding of experience.

Currently, the methodology is a special subject, an independent science. Based on this, Soviet and advanced scientists from foreign countries formulate specific concepts of the methodology of teaching a foreign language, its categories, laws, terms, tasks. The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language has been formed into an independent academic discipline. There is a fairly extensive literature on the teaching of Russian as a foreign language. In 1966. Russian Russian Language Teaching Research Center for Foreigners was established, which in 1974 was reorganized into the Pushkin Institute of the Russian Language. Russian Russian Language and Literature International Association (MAPRYAL) was formed in 1967, and the regularly published magazine "Russian Language Abroad" appeared.

The methodology of teaching Russian to foreigners, like any other methodology, is based on the conclusions and generalizations of a number of sciences, primarily linguistics, didactics and psychology.

The conclusions of linguistics, psychology and didactics form the scientific basis of the methodology of teaching the Russian language to foreigners.

The teaching methodology depends on different learning objectives and conditions, i.e. on non-linguistic factors.

The subject of the methodology is teaching the Russian language as a means of communication – it defines the ultimate goal – "to master the language".

Teaching Russian as a foreign language (and any subject in general) – this is a joint

activity of a teacher and students. In order for students to master the language, the teacher must carry out certain educational (instructional) actions: explain new material, give a task, ask a question and check the correctness of the answer, etc. Students should also be active and carry out a number of actions during the educational process: read the text, learn the words, perform exercises, answer questions from the teacher, etc.

In the usual forms of education (full-time) The actions of the students are always determined and directed by the teacher. It is he who decides what the students need to do, at what point, in what sequence, for what purpose. And, of course, he also determines what and how to do in class (even outside of class) for himself. He teaches directly and teaches students to learn. But any teacher knows that the teacher's teaching actions do not always give the desired result.

The basic science for the methodology is linguistics (linguistics). Teaching practice shows that not every way of describing the Russian language is equally effective when it is necessary to teach foreigners. Without the participation of linguistics, it is also impossible to make teaching effective.

Pedagogical factors should also be taken into account in the educational process. Among them there are such phenomena and patterns that are studied by general pedagogy. For example, the connection between education and upbringing.

This is especially important when teaching Russian, a country where more than 120 nationalities live. Didactic principles in language teaching Didactics is a department of pedagogy that outlines general teaching methods. Didactic – instructive, instructive.

Learning is a joint activity of a teacher and students. Now we need to clarify what has been said: learning is a joint active cognitive activity organized, motivated and supervised by a teacher. Let's look at this definition and at the same time formulate the most important didactic principles.

1. What is a "joint" activity? As already noted, the teacher and the students strive for the same common goal. In order to achieve it, both the teacher and the students must perform certain actions. And the teacher is obliged to ensure that the students do everything that is necessary and in the right sequence, with the right effect. Therefore, one of the main didactic principles is the principle of collectivity.

2. The second is the principle of activity. In order for learning to be effective, it is the students who must take the initiative, be able to independently and creatively approach the subject, be able to work independently in and out of the classroom. To ensure and organize the activity of students is the most important task of a teacher.

3. Didactics suggests how to ensure this activity. Students should be faced with a problem, to solve which they need the knowledge, skills, and abilities that are included in the curriculum. All training should turn into a solution to a number of problems that should constantly become more complicated. This is required by the didactic principle of problemativeness.

4. What does "feels the need" mean? This means that the problem posed to the student by itself does not yet ensure his activity. There must be a need to solve this problem, i.e. an appropriate motivation must be created. The motivating function of a teacher is the most important. The principle of motivation or the principle of motivation is a special didactic principle. A person learns a foreign language not only in order to use it for communication. In

addition to communication, cognitive motivation also works here. The very activity of students in language acquisition from the psychological side is a typical cognitive activity: as a result, students enrich themselves – their consciousness, their personality, their activities.

5. One of the important didactic principles is considered to be the principle of developmental learning. When teaching a foreign language, it means that we must set more and more complex communicative and cognitive tasks for students in a certain sequence. It should be noted that not every problem is didactically valuable and causes a student to have a motivated attitude towards it.

It may be too simple and therefore not intensive. Or it can be so difficult that the student will not immediately understand. The task or problem should, as it were, push the student forward, make him grow and develop.

6. The difficulty is also that the students are not the same. What is easy for one is difficult for the other. Some perceive information better with their "eyes", others with their "ears", one immediately joins in communication in the language being studied, others accumulate, comprehend, systematize language material for a very long time and only then decide to speak. To ensure the effectiveness of training, we must take into account the characteristics of both. Therefore, the principle of individualization is an important principle.

All the above-mentioned principles of any teaching should be implemented in the methodology of a particular subject, in our case, in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. All these principles are interrelated and suggest to us a completely specific model of the educational process.

Most of the patterns governing the educational process are of a psychological nature, which is why psychology is considered the main basic science for the methodology.

Conclusion. Firstly, these are the psychological patterns of assimilation. For example, psychology always indicates which ways to go in learning. There are psychological patterns specific to mastering the Russian language (or other foreign languages). For example, you cannot teach a language only in a conscious way. It is also advisable to use imitation (imitation) or independent adaptation to these conditions.

Secondly, these are psychological patterns of communication. We teach not so much language as speech in this language, communication with the help of this language. And to teach communication, you need to know how it is psychologically organized. Therefore, without the participation of communication psychology, modern methods cannot develop either.

Thirdly, these are psychological patterns related to the peculiarities of a language – a language in general or a specific one. The branch of psychology that deals with the connection of psychological processes with the structure of language is called psycholinguistics. The methodologist has to take into account other psychological factors: general patterns of perception, memory, thinking; individual differences of students, etc.

Activities can be not only communicative: there are work activities, cognitive (educational), and gaming. But it always has a fundamentally uniform psychological structure, which means that the patterns of its formation are also the same. It follows that both communication and training in such communication should be subject to general psychological patterns.

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